

ON THE MATURITY OF WORLD-WIDE FAILURE THEORIES: COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTS FOR $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: The authors are coordinating a 'World-Wide Failure Exercise' to establish the current status of theoretical methods for predicting structural failure in fibre reinforced composites materials. The exercise runs in two parts. Part A is devoted to providing full details of the theories together with predictions, made by their originators, for a standard set of test cases. Part B is concerned with comparing the theoretical predictions with experimental results. This paper is directed at exposing some of the early lessons resulting from Part A. Particular attention is focussed on three 'Test Cases', all involving $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply laminates. Theoretical predictions and experimental results are presented for the in-plane biaxial failure envelopes. Preliminary conclusions are drawn as to the degree of maturity of the current theories in dealing with the progression to failure, under a wide range of lamina combined stress states.

KEYWORDS: failure, laminates, biaxial, stresses, strength.

INTRODUCTION

A co-ordinated study (known as the 'World-Wide Failure Exercise') is currently being undertaken by the authors of this paper, aimed at providing a comprehensive description of the foremost failure theories for fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) laminates which are available at the present time, a comparison of their predictive capabilities directly with each other, and a comparison of their predictive capabilities against experimental data. In the 'exercise', selected workers in the area of fibre composite failure theories, including leading academics and developers of software/numerical codes, were invited to submit papers to a strictly controlled format. A series of laminate configurations, load cases and input data were clearly defined by the organisers. Test cases were selected to challenge the theories to the full, embodying a wide range of parameters. These included fibre type (carbon and glass), matrix type (different epoxies), lay-up configuration (unidirectional lamina and angle ply laminates, cross ply laminate, quasi-isotropic laminate and a generally oriented laminate) and loading conditions (which included uniaxial and biaxial situations).

A two-stage approach has been adopted for the exercise. Part A is devoted to providing full details of the theoretical models and failure criteria of the participants. Part B is concerned with comparing the theoretical results with experimental results. The arrangement allows both a 'blind test' and a further opportunity for participants to offer refinements to the theories. Part A, has just been completed, and published in a special edition of the journal 'Composite Science and Technology', which contains the philosophy adopted for the 'exercise' [1], a full description of the test cases chosen [2], papers submitted by the contributors describing their theory and its application to the test problems [3-14], and a direct comparison of the methodologies employed in each theory and the predictions made for each test case [15].

Part B is nearing completion. It will contain the experimental results, papers by the participants describing the correlation between experiment and their predictions, an overall comparison of the theories represented in the exercise against the experimental results and, finally, comments on the shortfalls in the theories and the experiments highlighted by the 'exercise'.

The present paper describes a 'slice' of the data that will be presented in Part B. It concentrates on comparing the theoretical predictions against available experimental results for the $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply glass/epoxy laminate, drawing particular attention to the areas where there is significant divergence.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST PROBLEMS

The $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP angle ply is used extensively, commercially, in applications such as piping, pressure vessels, and submersible structures. Three load ratios characterise their usage :-

- (1) Internal pressure with no end load (some piping), a hoop to axial stress ratio (SR) of 1/0.
- (2) Internal pressure (closed ended pressure vessel), giving a hoop to axial stress ratio of 2/1.
- (3) External pressure(submersible closed ended pressure vessel), giving a hoop to axial stress ratio of -2/-1.

In view of the widespread familiarity with this configuration, three of the test cases for the 'exercise' were based on it. Test Cases 9, 10 and 11 in [2] are, respectively :-

- Prediction of the complete in-plane (ie σ_x / σ_y) biaxial stress failure envelope (Test Case 9).
- Prediction of stress-strain curves under uniaxial tensile loading of $\sigma_y / \sigma_x=1/0$ (Test Case 10).
- Prediction of stress-strain curves under biaxial tensile loading of $\sigma_y / \sigma_x=2/1$ (Test Case 11).

Test Case 9 represents an exhaustive test for a failure theory. In predicting the entire in-plane (ie σ_x / σ_y) failure envelope for the $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP angle ply lay-up, a comprehensive range of combinations of longitudinal (σ_1), transverse (σ_2) and in-plane shear (τ_{12}) stress will be encountered at the lamina level. This will challenge the failure criteria employed to the full, particularly the methods used to discriminate between 'initial' and 'final' failure, and to represent the properties of partially failed material in the intervening phase.

The laminate defined by the organisers[2], consists of four plies oriented at $+55^\circ/-55^\circ/-55^\circ/+55^\circ$, as shown schematically in Fig 1. The material was E-glass/epoxy. The thickness of each ply was 0.25mm, with the mechanical and thermal properties as follows :-

$E_1=45.6$ (GPa), $E_2=16.2$ (GPa), G_{12} (initial)= 5.83 (Gpa),

$\nu_{12}=0.278$, $\nu_{23}=0.4$, $G_{IC}=165$ (J/m²),

α_1 (10⁻⁶/°C)=8.6, α_2 (10⁻⁶/°C)=26.4,

Stress free temperature=120 °C.

It should be noted that this GRP material exhibits highly nonlinear lamina in-plane shear stress strain behaviour. Participants were supplied with a full description of the nonlinear response, Ref[2].

Fig 1 A diagram showing the lay-up and loading of the $\pm 55^\circ$ laminate. The total thickness=1mm

DESCRIPTION OF THE FAILURE THEORIES

Table 1 lists the participants and indicates the fourteen theoretical approaches they employed. For the sake of simple identification and quick referencing, each of the theories is referred to by the single name listed in the last column (It does not necessarily imply the sole originator of the theory). It should be noted that Hart-Smith presented two complete papers, each containing a distinct theory. Sun and Chamis presented single papers, but employed two different analytical models in order to tackle the full range of test cases (ie there were some limitations which prevented the use of any one model for all cases).

Table 1 A summary of participants and approaches represented in the exercise.

Contributor(s)/originators	Approach represented	Theory designation
Gotsis, Chamis et al,[3]	-ICAN -CODSTRAN (micromechanics)	-Chamis (1) -Chamis (2)
Hart-Smith[8]	Generalised Tresca theory.	Hart-Smith(1)
Hart-Smith[7]	Maximum strain theory	Hart-Smith(2)
Eckold[4]	British Standard pressure vessel design codes	Eckold
Edge[5]	British Aerospace, In-house design method	Edge
McCartney[6]	Physically based 'Damage Mechanics'	McCartney
Puck and Schürmann[9]	Physically based 3-D phenomenological model	Puck
Wolfe and Butalia[13]	Maximum strain energy method	Wolfe
Sun and Tao[11]	Linear analysis Non-linear analysis (non-linear is FE based)	Sun (L) Sun(NL)
Zinoviev et al[14]	Development of Maximum stress theory	Zinoviev
Tsai and Liu[12]	Interactive progressive quadratic failure criterion	Tsai
Rotem[10]	Interactive matrix and fibre failure theory	Rotem

Full details of the characteristics of each theory can be found in the individual papers, and a summary in [15]. There are two notable points :-

The approach offered by Eckold [4] was based on the philosophy embodied in the British Standards for FRP pressure vessels. Thus his predictions are intended to reflect safe design limits (ie for continuous service, environments etc), **and not failure**, thereby providing what would be expected to be a lower bound to the exercise.

McCartney provided an approach based on damage mechanics. Though predictions were given for some of the test cases in the exercise, none were provided in Part A for the $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP angle ply, which suggests that the method may be a little immature.

THEORETICAL RESULTS

The organisers provided the participants with identical test case definition information [2]. However some of the theories offered, contained assumptions which impinged on the way the input information was interpreted. Key differences were as follows :-

Detection of Failure

Most of the participants applied criteria for detecting failure at the lamina level. As a consequence, a variety of models were proposed for dealing with interactions between σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} . Readers may gain a better insight into the interaction assumptions by referring to Fig(3) in [15], which summarises results from Test Case No. 3 from the 'exercise', featuring the biaxial failure envelope of a lamina under combined σ_1 and σ_2 loading. It should be noted that no two theories employed the same approach and as a consequence, each theory generated a unique set of failure envelopes in the three planes (σ_1 - τ_{12} , σ_2 - τ_{12} and σ_1 - σ_2).

Residual Thermal Stresses

All of the participants were aware of the importance of residual thermal stresses which result from the elevated cure process. However, less than half (Edge, McCartney, Puck, Sun and Tsai) attempted to take them into account in failure prediction. Even then there were differences in methodology. Puck, for instance, opted to take into account only 50% of the thermal stresses, on the grounds that relaxation with time, due to moisture absorption and the accompanying swelling, dissipates the remaining 50%. On the other hand, Tsai introduced a 0.5% moisture content in his calculation and he assumed a temperature difference of -100°C in all the laminates analysed. No information had been provided to participants (or asked for) concerning the effects of moisture, so this introduction was unexpected. In the event, the moisture and thermal stresses effectively cancelled each other out [12].

Lamina Properties Used For Initial Failure

Most participants used the lamina stress or strain data provided by the organisers to compute the onset of initial failure. This data had been derived from tests on isolated lamina, in a conventional manner. Sun, Hart-Smith and Rotem argued that certain properties of a lamina are higher when they are embedded within a laminate (ie in-situ) than when measured on isolated laminae. To take account of the in-situ effects, Sun assumed that the transverse tensile strength of an in-situ lamina was 50% higher than that of an isolated lamina. Rotem assumed the transverse strength and transverse Young's modulus of an in-situ lamina was 20% higher than that of isolated one. Hart-Smith assumed that the transverse tensile strength should be such that the lamina would first fail either in shear or in fibre failure.

In order to account for nonlinear material behaviour without resorting to sophisticated programming, Hart-Smith considered that the lamina shear and transverse moduli taken in the calculation of strength should be those corresponding to the secant values.

Modelling the Post Initial Failure Response

Once failure was detected in a lamina, most of the models used some form of ply discount process ie the Young's modulus associated with the mode of failure (and occasionally the Poisson's ratio) was decreased either abruptly or gradually. Details of how the post failure

mechanisms were carried out are provided in [15]. Briefly, all these models shared the following common features

- All rely on applying criteria to stresses or strains at the lamina level and expressed in lamina coordinate axes.
- All assume that fibre failure, be it in tension or in compression, constitutes final failure.
- Almost all models distinguish between failures under transverse tension and that under transverse compression. Here the term ‘transverse’ is used to refer to the direction perpendicular to the fibres in a lamina.

However, the post failure methods employed do differ and, for sake of simplicity, they can be classified into three main groups:

- Models employing sudden reduction in the properties of the failed lamina. These are presented by Tsai, Wolfe and Sun (L).
- Models employing a gradual drop in the properties of the failed lamina. These are represented by Puck, Edge, Rotem, Zinoviev, Rotem, Chamis and Sun (NL).
- Models not employing any post failure methods (Hart-Smith and Eckold).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

The specimens tested were filament wound glass/epoxy tubes produced by the Defence Evaluation and Research Agency (DERA, Fort Halstead, Kent, UK). Two modes of testing were performed, the first on virgin tubes and the second with a non load bearing, flexible liner in place. ‘Initial’ failure was characterised by weeping or jetting of the test liquid (oil) through the tube wall (ie with no liner present). ‘Final’ failure was signified by catastrophic rupture, sometimes prefaced by significant damage and deformation well before the endpoint. Full details of the experimental biaxial testing programme are provided in Refs[16,17].

Values of leakage and catastrophic failure stress at the specific stress ratios of 1/0, 2/1 and -2/-1 are given in Table 2.

Table 2 Experimental failure results on $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP laminates under uniaxial and biaxial load.

	Stress ratio SR= σ_y / σ_x		
	1/0	2/1	-2/-1
	Failure Stress σ_y MPa	Failure Stress σ_y MPa	Failure Stress σ_y MPa
Leakage Failure	386	280	None
Final Catastrophic Failure	595	736	-792

COMPARISON OF THEORY AND EXPERIMENT

Test Case 9 - Biaxial failure envelopes

Figs 2(a) and 2(b) show a comparison between the predicted and the measured ‘final’ failure envelopes for the $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP angle ply laminate.

Figure 2(a) Biaxial Final Failure Envelope for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP angle ply lay-up

Figure 2(b) Biaxial Final Failure Envelope for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP angle ply lay-up

Theoretical predictions for ‘initial’ and ‘final’ failure strength at three stress ratios (namely $SR=1/0$, $SR=2/1$ and $SR=-2/-1$) are presented in Figs(3), (4) and (5) respectively. The predictions have been normalised by dividing by the experimental values contained in Table 2, using the assumption that ‘initial’ failure equates to the experimentally observed leakage event, and ‘final’ failure equates to the experimentally observed catastrophic rupture event.

Strength Prediction, SR = 1/0

For initial failure stress prediction, all the theoretical curves underestimated the measured leakage strength (Fig 3a) by approximately 55% on average. The lower bound prediction was provided by Eckold (0.17) and the upper bound was provided by Puck (0.85).

For final failure stress prediction, the general fit between the theories and the experiment was poor (Fig 3b). The lower bound prediction was provided by Chamis (0.24) and the upper bound was provided by Eckold (1.10). Again, all of the theories underestimated the observed values by around 50%, with the exception of Eckold. In constructing the final failure envelope, Eckold did not use the strain limit criteria suggested in the British Standard. Thus, the high failure strengths reported here were much higher than the standard would predict (see the stress strain curves in [4]).

In general, the theories tended to predict an initial in-plane shear mode of failure and in the majority of the theories, the initial and final failures are coincident.

Fig 3. Bar charts showing the ratio of theoretical/experimental failure stresses for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP laminate under SR=1/0

Strength Prediction, SR = 2/1

For initial failure stress prediction, all the theoretical curves underestimated the measured leakage strength (Fig 4a) by approximately 38% on average. The lower bound prediction was provided by Chamis (0.16) and the upper bound was provided by Eckold (0.6).

For final failure stress prediction, the general fit between the theories and the experiment was fair. Nine of the twelve theories predicted strengths in the range 1.07 to 1.35 of the observed value (ie were unconservative). The lower bound was provided by Wolfe (0.15) and the upper bound by Hart-Smith (1.33).

Fig 4. Bar charts showing the ratio of theoretical/experimental failure stresses for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP laminate under SR = 2/1

In general, the theories tended to predict an initial transverse tensile mode of failure, leading eventually to final longitudinal (fibre) failure.

Strength Prediction, SR = -2/-1

Experimental observations showed that there was no intermediate leakage mode of failure, the specimens failing catastrophically with no prior evidence of damage accumulation. The theories predicted different modes of failure ranging from shear to transverse compression to longitudinal (fibre) compression.

The general fit between the theories and the experiment was fair (Fig 5). Nine of the eleven predictions were grouped between 0.5 and 0.77 of the observed value, the lower bound being provided by Chamis (0.25) and the upper bound by Eckold (1.0).

Fig 5. Bar charts showing the ratio of theoretical/experimental failure stresses for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP laminate under SR = -2/-1

Accuracy of Strength Prediction

There are significant variations in the shapes of the envelopes, those of Rotem and Wolfe being the smallest and those of Hart-Smith being the largest. As a first order discriminator, the theories can be divided into two groups :-

Conservative Theories (ie where no part of the predicted envelope exceeds the experimental results) :- Tsai, Rotem , Wolfe.

Unconservative Theories (ie where some part of the predicted envelope exceeds the experimental results) :- Chamis, Puck, Edge, Zinoviev, Hart-Smith (1), Hart-Smith (2), Eckold, and Sun.

The results of the first order comparison between theory and experiment, at the three primary stress ratios for this $\pm 55^\circ$ laminate, are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Range of strength predictions expressed as a fraction of the experimental values

Biaxial Stress State		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	'Median' Value
SR = 1/0	Initial Failure	0.17	0.85	0.55
	Final Failure	0.24	1.07	0.49
SR = 2/1	Initial Failure	0.16	0.6	0.37
	Final Failure	0.15	1.33	0.98
SR = -2/-1	Initial Failure	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Final Failure	0.25	1.04	0.63

CONCLUSIONS

From a designer's perspective the $\pm 55^\circ$ glass/epoxy laminate test cases from the 'World Wide Failure Exercise' have highlighted the following :-

- The theories show a lack of unanimity in predicting failure strength and indeed each theory produced a unique failure envelope with some extreme differences in evidence.
- A comparison between the theoretical and experimental 'final failure' envelopes showed that the Tsai, Rotem, and Wolfe theories were conservative throughout.
- The theories of Puck, Edge, Chamis, Sun and Zinoviev matched the experimental data fairly well in shape and magnitude in some parts of the envelope.
- The theories of Eckold, Hart-Smith(1) and Hart Smith(2) showed some significant deviations from experiment in certain areas (as evidenced by the more detailed comparison, at the three primary stress ratios for the $\pm 55^\circ$ laminate).
- All of the theories underpredicted the strength at which 'initial failure' occurred experimentally, as defined by leakage of fluid in these test cases. This may be attributable to the fact that the onset of 'initial' failure for the tubular test specimen may not be sufficient to produce leakage. Additional loading may be necessary in order to evolve a fully connected crack path through the tube wall from the inside to the outside. Clearly there is still a need to develop the failure theories somewhat further in order to provide more accurate predictions of leakage failure stress.
- Less than half of the theoreticians have attempted to take curing stresses into account in their analyses. Based on a simplistic linear thermo-elastic calculation, the inclusion of that stress component would lead to (a) a reduction in the initial strength prediction by 40% for those zones of the envelope where initial failure is dominated by transverse tension and (b) an increase in the predicted initial failure stress in those zones of the envelope where initial failure is dominated by transverse compression. The lack of unanimity over their treatment by the theoreticians raises the question 'is it right to ignore residual thermal stresses ?'.
- Three participants (Sun, Rotem and Hart-Smith) argued that certain properties of a lamina are higher when they are embedded within a laminate (ie in-situ) than when measured on isolated laminae. In the extreme case, Hart-Smith's theories assumed that the lines representing transverse tensile failure should always lie beyond those corresponding to shear or fibre failure, and he assumed that the secant moduli should be used in place of the initial moduli. His results indicate that these assumptions tend to provide an overestimation in comparison with experiment under certain conditions (Figs 2(a), 2(b), and 4(b)). From a designers viewpoint, there is no cohesive theory available to predict in-situ properties as a function of laminate configuration. The question 'should we correct for in-situ effects and, if so, how ?', remains open.
- The test cases involved a widely used glass/epoxy system which exhibits a highly non-linear in-plane shear stress/strain response. Such behaviour is entirely typical for the majority of polymer composite systems used today, thereby indicating that a truly generalised failure theory must contain the means to handle such behaviour, if accurate strength and stress-strain behaviour is to be predicted. Although the evidence is not shown in this paper, the early indications from test cases 9,10 and 11 are that all of the theories presented here are deficient to a greater or lesser extent in this area. It is one of the factors which has contributed to the substantial gap between the experiments and the 14 theories employed.

Readers are reminded that a more comprehensive picture of the current status of failure prediction theories, including further refinement of the theoretical results presented here, will

emerge when Part B of the 'Failure Exercise' is published in the near future. Several of the conclusions drawn by the authors may require revision in the light of this further information.

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